

A STUDY ON EMPLOYEE PERCEPTION TOWARDS HR PRACTICES IN INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY SHANTHI IT SOLUTION

JEGANATH K¹, DR.S.MADHIYARSI²

¹*MBA Student of Jerusalem College of Engineering, Chennai, Tamil Nadu, India,,*

²*Professor, Jerusalem College of Engineering, Chennai, Tamil Nadu, India*

ABSTRACT- The main aim of this research is to know the Employee's Perception of HR Practices followed in the organization. The study is descriptive in nature. The objective of the study is to know the employees perception towards HR practices such as perception of internal communication level of training and development performance management, to find out whether the employees are satisfied with the HR Practices followed in the organization. The sample size is 150. The sample method used for this study is the chi square and ANOVA. The data has been collected through a well-structured questionnaire and has been analyzed with the help of SPSS package.

Keywords: *Employee Perception, Employee Feedback, Communication, performance management.*

INTRODUCION:

HR practices means that human resources personnel can develop the leadership of employees.

This occurs in the practice of developing extensive training courses and motivational programs, such as devising systems to direct and assist management in performing ongoing performance appraisals.

Organization is a place where the entire employees are going to work together.

Commonly in any organization perception towards the work and organizational Human resource practices play a very important role. The best HR practices in an organization are going to create a good working culture of the organization.

HR best practices are a set of processes and techniques that have been proven by research and experience to produce increased business performance results. They are internal guidelines that a company establishes to streamline procedures and obtain optimum results in all business areas. A firm HRM practices refers to the

policies, practices, and systems that influence employees' behavior, attitudes, and performance. It is sometimes referred to as involving "people practices".

REVIEW OF LITERATURE:

Singh, A. k. 2009

HRM PRACTICES AND ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE IN SELECTED PRIVATE SECTOR ORGANIZATIONS". The review of literature has identified that the major chunk of research in India emanates from descriptive data and experience sharing, which does not serve certain practice-oriented concerns. The questionnaire consists of 90 items, of which 69 items concern HRM practices of the organization, and 21 items concern organization culture. The correlation analysis has been used to infer the relationship between variables of HRM practices and organizational culture. A healthy culture is required for utilizing and enhancing employee competencies and to develop people.

Jarad, , I. y. 2010

"Organizational Culture and Organizational Performance 60 research studies". Covering 7619 companies and small business units in 26 countries have found that market culture and business performance are strongly related. This positive correlation is identified by more than 35 performance measures. Organizational culture was based more on differences in norms and shared practices, which was learned at the workplace and considered as valid within the boundaries of a particular organization. Hence, in the context of organizational culture, cultural differences resided more on practices while national, the differences lie in values.

Alnaqbi, w. 2011

“The relationship between human resource practices and employee retention in public organizations”. The purpose of this study was to identify HR practices and other factors such as job satisfaction, organizational commitments and leadership practice that affect employee retention in the UAE with emphasis on public organizations, in a comparative study of Sharjah and Dubai. To accomplish this task, both quantitative and qualitative research approaches were employed. The results show that national culture has a direct influence on organizational culture.

SAIFULISLAM. 2014

“Human Resource Management Practices: Influence of recruitment and selection, and training and development on the organizational performance”. The sample comprises staff and lecturers of the university. To achieve the study objectives, the researchers developed a questionnaire, which was administered in a survey. The collected data were analyzed by using SPSS. The analysis of the descriptive statistics and correlations indicated that recruitment and selection as well as training and development significantly correlated with the organizational performance.

MADANAT, H. G. 2018

RESOURCE MANAGEMENT PRACTICES AND ITS IMPACT ON EMPLOYEES’ SATISFACTION”. A questionnaire was developed and administered to 540 employees in the banking sector of Jordan out of which 406 were returned to test research hypotheses. The findings revealed a high level of effectiveness of all HRM practices combined and for four individual practices while a medium level of compensation effectiveness was yielded. It has been found that employees’ satisfaction level was medium. A strong positive relationship has been identified between the effectiveness of HRM and employees’ satisfaction. The study recommended improving the financial compensation system of banks, which would positively increase the level of employees’ satisfaction.

NEED FOR STUDY

The need of the study is to analyze various dimensions of employees' perception of HR practices and its impact on satisfaction of employees. To know what are the few more hr practices could be adopted for the development of the organization.

This paper explores the fundamental principles and best practices of ERM, emphasizing the importance of clear communication, conflict resolution, and employee feedback mechanisms.

ERM IS a vital component for building a cohesive and motivated workforce in today's competitive business environment

SCOPE OF STUDY

This study is aimed at understanding the employee’s perception of HR practices at IT Industry. This study is confined to the employees of IT Industry. This study tries to address the relationship between employees' perception and its impact on Satisfaction in IT Industry.

It covers the implementation of ERM systems, the role of technology in facilitating employee interactions, and the integration of ERM practices with organizational culture.

The study also examines the challenges organizations face in maintaining effective employee relationships and proposes strategies to overcome these obstacles.

LIMITATIONS OF STUDY

Few employees feel that they need more organization to encourage employees to suggest product/process improvement in HR practices. Organizations get team opinion and ideas before making decisions. The employees are encouraged to take initiatives and do

things on their way. Our organization places the right person in the right job.

OBJECTIVES OF STUDY

Primary Objective:

To study Employee Perception towards HR practices in Information Technology Industry.

Secondary Objectives:

- To know the level of employee satisfaction based on their perception.
- To analyze the ethical culture contacts of the HR practices from employee's assumption.
- To analyze the internal environment contacts of the HR of an organization.
- To provide suggestions to improve HR practices followed in the organization.

METHODOLOGY:

The methodology is the general research strategy that outlines the way in which research is to be undertaken and, among other things, identifies the methods to be used in it. These methods, described in the methodology, define the means or modes of data collection or, sometimes, how a specific result is to be calculated. Methodology does not define specific methods, even though much attention is given to the nature and kinds of processes to be followed in a particular procedure or to attain an objective.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION:

PERCENTAGE ANALYSIS FOR GENDER OF THE RESPONDENTS

S.NO	AGE	NO.OFRESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
1	20-30years	97	64.7%
2	31-40years	32	21.3%
3	41-50years	15	10%
4.	Above 50 Years	6	4%
	Total	150	100

INFERENCE

From the above table its shown that out of 100 employees 65% are 20-30 years , 21% are 31-40years, 10% and 41-50years, and 4% are Above 50 years.

PERCENTAGE ANALYSIS FOR GENDER OF THE RESPONDENTS

S.NO	Gender	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Male	72	48%
2	Female	78	52%
	Total	150	100

INFERENCE

From the above table its shown that out of 100 employees 48% are male, 52% TO 40 female.

PERCENTAGE ANALYSIS FOR EDUCATION QUALIFICATION OF THE EMPLOYEES

Educational qualification	No.of Respondents	Percentage
HSC	7	4.7%
UG	97	64.7%
PG	45	30%
Diploma	1	0.7%
Total	150	100

INFERENCE:

From the above table show that out of 100 employees 5% are HSC ,65% are ug ,65% are pg and 1% are diploma.

PERCENTAGE ANALYSIS FOR DESIGNATION OF THE EMPOLYEEES

Annual Income	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Less than 30000	50	33.3%
30001 to 40000	24	16%
40001 to 50000	28	18.7%
50001 to 60000	25	16.7%

60001 to 70000	10	6.7%
Above 1,00,000	13	8.7%
Total	150	100

INFERENCE:

From the above table show that out of 100employees 33% are less than 30000 ,16% are 30001 to 40000 ,19% are 40001 to 50000,17% are 50001 to 60000 , 60001 to 70000 are 7% and 9% are 100000.

CHI SQUARE

Null hypothesis(H0): There is no significant relationship between Gender of respondents and employee perception in the organization.

Alternate hypothesis (H1): There is a significant relationship between gender of respondents and employee perception in the organization.

	Results					Row Totals
	Strongly agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly disagree	
Male	10 (14.40) [1.34]	20 (16.20) [0.89]	10 (10.80) [0.06]	8 (7.20) [0.09]	6 (5.40) [0.07]	54
Female	30 (25.60) [0.76]	25 (28.80) [0.50]	20 (19.20) [0.03]	12 (12.80) [0.05]	9 (9.60) [0.04]	96
<i>Column Totals</i>	40	45	30	20	15	150 (Grand Total)

The chi-square statistic is 3.8291. The p-value is .42963. The result is *not* significant $p < .05$.

Since the pH value is greater than 0.05 so an alternative hypothesis is rejected and the null hypothesis is accepted so there is no relationship between the gender of respondents and employee perception in the organization.

ANOVA

To find out the significance between how do you foster a sense of trust and respect between managers and employees and How do you describe the company culture

H0 : there is no significance difference between how do you foster a sense of trust and respect between managers and employees and How do you describe the company culture

H1: there is an significance difference between how do you foster a sense of trust and respect between managers and employees and How do you describe the company culture

ANOVA

Null hypothesis (H0): There is no significant relationship between the factors Employee perception and HR practices.

Alternate hypothesis (H02): There is a significant relationship between the factors of Employee perception and HR practices.

Analysis of Variance Results

F-statistic value = 1.47728

P-value = 0.3348

Data Summary				
Groups	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	Std. Error
Group 1	2	20	14.1421	10
Group 2	2	22.5	3.5355	2.5
Group 3	2	15	7.0711	5
Group 4	2	10	2.8284	2
Group 5	2	7.5	2.1213	1.5

ANOVA Summary					
Source	Degrees of Freedom	Sum of Squares	Mean Square	F-Stat	P-Valu
	DF	SS	MS		
Between Groups	4	325	81.25	1.4773	0.3348
Within Groups	5	274.999	54.9998		
Total:	9	599.999			

FINDINGS

Majority 64.7% of the respondents are aged between 20-30 years.

Majority 52% of the respondents are Female.

Majority 64.7% of the respondents are UG students.

Majority 33.3% of the respondents are less than 30000.

Majority 68% of the respondents are unmarried.

Majority 22% of the respondents strongly agree with job enrichment.

Majority 102 % of the respondents agree with job rotation.

Majority 49 % of the respondents are neutral Work modules and flexi-time.

Majority 59.3% of the respondents are satisfied the organization encourages employees to suggest product/process improvement.

Majority 51.3% of the respondents agree the organization has the practice of carrying employee attitude/employee satisfaction surveys.

Majority 49.3% of the respondents are good clear about your work/ job responsibilities.

Majority 54.7% of the respondents agree we are assigned challenging jobs to charge our enthusiasm and develop our skills.

Majority 64.7% of the respondents agree organizations get team opinion and ideas before making decisions.

Majority 64.7% of the respondents have good views regarding the working environment in the IT Sector.

Majority 57.3% of the respondents agree. Employees are encouraged to take initiatives and do things on their way.

Majority 54% of the respondents agree our organization places the right person in the right job.

Majority 49.3% of the respondents agree you are being paid adequately for the work you do.

Majority 71.8% of the respondents agree. Training in our organization includes social skills, general problem solving skills and broader knowledge of the organization and business.

Majority 48.60% of the respondents are highly satisfied in human resource planning.

Majority 49.30 % of the respondents are highly satisfied in employment development

Majority 60% of the respondents agree.

Majority 60% of the respondents are satisfied Salary/ Monetary incentives are sufficient in your organizations.

Majority 62.7% of the respondents strongly agree. Performance appraisal is a part of the performance management system.

Majority 56.7% of the respondents agree HR practices are flexible in your organization towards the Environment.

SUGGESTIONS

The management can adopt a new method of appraisal than the present tool performance evaluation sheet. They can adopt 360 degree appraisal. Employees should be considered for the increment in salary. If their performance exceeds predetermined standards. Employees should be given a chance to express their thoughts and ideas for organization benefit. New technologies should be adopted.

REFERENCES

1. Naeem Akhter, Aizaz Hussain (2016) "Impact of HR Practices on Job Satisfaction: A Study on Teachers of Private and Public Sector", International Review of Management

and Business Research Vol. 5 Issue.2 ISSN: 2306-9007.

2. Harsh Purohit, Poonam Malik and S.C. Malik (2014)" Impact of HR Practices on Job Satisfaction Level of Managerial Employees in Textile Units" International Journal of Statistics and Reliability Engineering Vol. 1 (2), pp. 140-154, 2014 (ISSN: 23500174).
3. Mehvish Mehmood (2017) "Impact of human resource development (HRD) practices on employee's performance in textile industry" International Journal of Academic Research and Development, Volume 2; Issue 6; November 2017; Page No. 970-973.
4. Kennedy Alusa, Anne Kariuki (2015) "Human Resource Management Practices, Employee Outcome and Performance of Coffee Research Foundation, Kenya" European Journal of Business and Management, 7, No.3, 2015
5. Rabindra Kumar Pradhan, Sangya Dash, Lalatendu Kesari Jena (2017) "Do HR Practices Influence Job Satisfaction? Examining the Mediating Role of Employee Engagement in Indian Public Sector Undertakings" Journal of Sage publication Global Business Review.
6. Khurram Shahzad, Sajid Bashir and Muhammad I Ramay (2018) "Impact of HR Practices on Perceived Performance of University Teachers in Pakistan" International Review of Business Research Papers Vol. 4 No.2 March 2008 Pp.302-315.
7. Ying Wang, Sunghoon Kim (2020) "Employee Perceptions of HR Practices: A Critical Review and Future Directions" The International Journal of HRM. <https://www.tandfonline.com/loi/trjh20>